

THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGIC TOURISM AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT IN THE SAMARKAND REGION

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Annotation: *The article discusses in detail the concepts and meanings of the development of ecological tourism in Samarkand. current state and prospects for its development. The world experience of countries in the field of ecological tourism and their role in the development of the tourism industry in the city of Samarkand was studied. The significance of the study of the article is due to the rapid development of the ecologic tourism industry in the city of Samarkand.*

Key words: *Samarkand, economy, ecologic tourism, development, traveling, ecologic tourism industry, relationship, tourist, revenue, visitors, local.*

It is known that the state has identified a number of priority tasks to eliminate problematic situations that arise in the field of ecologic tourism during the formation of a new Uzbekistan. In particular, the number of domestic tourists will increase to 12 million as part of the Travel Uzbekistan program in the third priority area of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026. The strategy also provides for an increase in the number of foreign tourists visiting the republic to 9 million people. In this regard, conducting scientific research on the development of ecological tourism and improving its efficiency is a hot topic.

In the course of the study, the best practices of foreign countries in the development of ecologic tourism were studied. Used official statistics on ecologic tourism in the city of Samarkand. The article effectively used such methods as statistical observation, systematic approach, generalization, comparative analysis and synthesis.

Post-tandem period tourism has undergone many changes. These changes have also affected the sphere of eco-tourism. In many countries, ecologic tourism is one of the rapidly developing branches of the national economy, and in some of them - a fundamental branch of the economy, largely determining the development of the country. Tourism has become an important socio-economic phenomenon, which is associated with an increase in the level of a person's life and his need for rest. Tourism ranks third in the world after the income from the export of oil and petroleum products, weapons, cars. And eco-tourism accounts for a quarter of the total share of tourism. In addition, every sixteenth workplace falls on the tourism business. The role of ecologic tourism in the national economy is very great, which, in turn. It makes it necessary to thoroughly study not only the practical aspects of its functioning in the conditions of

the national economy, but also the features of the formation and basic characteristics of tourism itself as a scientific category.

Tourism and ecologic tourism currently plays a huge role for Uzbekistan in a good scenario, with the right strategy for its development, it can cause the economic growth of the country with its subsequent integration into the world economy. Since today the world ecologic tourism is rightfully. It is a highly profitable and dynamically developing sector of the state economy. Being a source of foreign currency inflow into the country, it affects its balance of payments, cultural and social spheres.

The significance of the article's research is due to the rapid development of the eco-tourism industry in the city of Samarkand, its transformation into an integral part of the national economy. Already today, in many countries, eco-tourism is one of the rapidly developing branches of the national economy, and in some of them - the fundamental branch of the economy, largely determining the development of the country. What has been said actualizes the importance of a thorough study of not only the practical aspects of the functioning of tourism and ecologic tourism in the conditions of the world economy and Samarkand, but also features of the formation and basic characteristics of tourism itself as a scientific category. The tourism potential of Samarkand is quite high, but it is used very poorly and often irrationally. In this regard the need to comprehend and scientifically search for optimal strategies and directions for the use and development of the natural resource, scientific and technical, economic and social, recreational and tourist potential of Samarkand and the districts that determine the prospects for its integration into the world economy system also actualizes the topic we have chosen.

The given argumentation allows us to speak about the scientific, theoretical and practical significance of the research that led to the choice of the topic. Ecologic tourism in Samarqand is a journey to a land where the sun shines almost all year round, to the realm of dry hot summer, warm winter, soft honey autumn and bright blooming spring. Nature has created landscapes of Samarqand in soft pastel colors with a predominance of yellow, copper, ochre, dark green and blue. With elegant strokes, she painted on canvas both arid deserts covered with golden sands, and gray steppes, and green valleys that in spring are covered with a red velvet carpet of flowering poppies, and murmuring mountain rivers, and picturesque blue lakes. But the mountains turned out to be the most picturesque: from low mountain ranges in the northern part to a powerful rocky ridge with steep cliffs in the south – they do not leave any traveler indifferent. Few people know that Samarqand is not only a great cultural heritage, blue domes of minarets, soaring upwards for many centuries, noisy oriental bazaars, but also incredible and delightful nature. Traveling in Uzbekistan, it is definitely worth combining visits to ancient cities with small insiders into the life of real mountain villages, mountain hikes or nights in the desert. Ecologic tourism in Samarqand as a full-fledged and independent part of the entire tourism industry, began to develop not so long ago. As you know, before, foreign citizens needed a registration

for every night of their stay in Samarqand. The registration rule is still in effect, but it has become possible to register at a campsite or as an independent traveler. However, we still do not recommend that you stay outside hotels or guest houses for more than 3 days on your own, unaccompanied by a travel company or guide. There are a lot of natural monuments and places in Samarqand where you can feel unity with nature.

The development and promotion of ecologic tourism acts and has a positive impact on the municipal and economic course and the development of rural areas where ecological areas are actually located. The development of the environmental services sector in Samarkand will lead to an increase in the number and scale of economic entities, thereby increasing the employment and income growth of women and youth. Assessing the dynamics of eco-tourism in the Samarkand region, the coronavirus pandemic in 2020 had a negative impact on the development of ecologic tourism. Improper and excessive use of natural habitats in rural areas of the Samarkand region, unregulated property relations have led to the destruction of these habitats, preventing the formation of incentives and benefits for long-term investment, restoration and improvement. We have studied the dynamics of income from ecologic tourism services. In the course of our research, we interviewed 258 local residents of different ages to assess the conditions at ecologic tourism facilities in Samarkand. According to the results of the study, there is a high interest in ecologic tourism and the need to work to improve the conditions of tourism at existing ecologic tourism facilities in the Samarkand region, the need to implement major investment projects to improve ecologic tourism infrastructure. Nature based tourism — “is all forms of tourism, enjoying natural resources in a wild or undeveloped natural areas: birdwatching, camping, hiking, fishing, hunting, photography etc.”. Ecologic tourism is defined as “responsible travel to wild nature which conserves the environment and improves the welfare of a local people”. Distinctive features of ecologic tourism are the satisfaction of the recreational demand of the visitor and hosts, without negative impact on the ecology of the region and with benefit to local population — “Eco” is obliged to serve for the good of nature, its biodiversity and ecology. It should be emphasized that development of ecologic tourism contributes to an increase in the environmental, educational and cultural level of society.

In order to make a feasible contribution to the further development nature based and ecologic tourism in Uzbekistan, to identify the real situation in places of recreation in the Samarkand Region, we conducted a study of the features of the nature based tourism potential in these recreation areas. To identify the public opinion of the local population of Samarkand Region about the preferences of a country vacation in the region a social survey was conducted. The author considered it appropriate to identify the following aspects:

- types of recreation in the lap of nature (active, passive relaxations, health healing & meditation, scientific research, etc.);
 - popular active type of rest in the Samarkand Region natural areas (hiking, skiing, bacycling, swimming, climbing, etc.);

- average duration of rest of the local people in the natural areas;
 - concretization by matching popular vocation spots on a map.
- Nature based tourism — “is all forms of tourism, enjoying natural resources in a wild or undeveloped natural areas: birdwatching, camping, hiking, fishing, hunting, photography etc.”

Ecologic tourism is defined as “responsible travel to wild nature which conserves the environment and improves the welfare of a local people”. The development and promotion of ecologic tourism acts and has a positive impact on the municipal and economic course and the development of rural areas where ecological areas are actually located. The development of the environmental services sector in Samarkand will lead to an increase in the number and scale of economic entities, thereby increasing the employment and income growth of women and youth. Assessing the dynamics of ecotourism in the Samarkand region, the coronavirus pandemic had a negative impact on the development of ecologic tourism. Improper and excessive use of natural habitats in rural areas of the Samarkand region, unregulated property relations have led to the destruction of these habitats, preventing the formation of incentives and benefits for long-term investment, restoration and improvement. We have studied the dynamics of income from ecologic tourism services. In the course of our research, we interviewed 158 local residents of different ages to assess the conditions at ecologic tourism facilities in Samarkand. In general, according to the results of our survey, there is a high interest in ecologic tourism and the need to improve tourist conditions in existing ecologic tourism places in the Samarkand region, which requires the implementation of large investment projects to improve ecologic tourism infrastructure.

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